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Critical Assessment of Democratic Autonomy in India

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Abstract

India is the largest democracy in the world in terms of accommodating plural identities of the vast population throughout the country. The resilience of both the Indian Constitution and democratic institutions of India deserves well-articulated research. However, the importance of autonomy and the role of civil society have been a much-neglected domain when it comes to studying Indian democracy. There is a need to study the convergence and divergence between the State and civil society to understand Indian democracy better. The ideas of David Held on 'democratic autonomy' holds significant importance to test Indian democracy in full light. An attempt has been made to see up to what extent Indian democracy has achieved democratic autonomy until now. The research paper attempts to delve deeper into the role of the State, institutions, women's autonomy, patriarchal politics, justice, governmentality and civil society to assess the Indian democracy. Qualitative text analysis method has been adopted for the research where primary and secondary sources have been taken to account.

Keywords

Autonomy, Civil Society, Democracy, India, State

Introduction

India is the largest democracy in the world and presents a suitable model to be studied as it has successfully accommodated diverse strata of societies for decades. The role of institutions, governmentality and civil society assumes significant importance in the flourishing of any democracy. The Constitution of India has proved to be the wisdom document in maintaining harmony among various institutions. Its resilience and sanctity have been widely appreciated all over the world. However, there is a need to assess the reality at ground zero of the constitutional values and democratic functioning of various autonomous institutions in India. Considering such a context, the 'democratic autonomy' model proposed by David Held for thriving democracy can prove to

be successful in the assessment of democratic autonomy in India. Therefore, this model has been used as an ideal framework to assess Indian democracy.

Democratic Autonomy and Governmentality

According to David Held, under the model of democratic autonomy,

...Obligations would clearly exist. Citizens would be obliged to accept democratic decisions in a variety of circumstances- at sites of politics, work and community life- unless it could be proved that their rights were violated by such decisions. But the obligation to get involved in all aspects of public life would not be a legal obligation. The right to a life of one's own, within a framework of democratic autonomy, is indisputably important (Held 184).

With the advent of time, autonomy has broadened its definition where "the idea of autonomy became not only the standard of rights or responsibilities, but also an issue of governmentality- something that denotes transaction, government, negotiation, and relating to others on the basis of set rules" (Samaddar). Therefore, Indian democracy cannot neglect the vital importance of autonomy as it is deeply entrenched with the governmentality. State concerns itself with the core ideas of territory and sovereignty while "governmentality concerns itself with the techniques of government, and these techniques of government are contestable" (Miller 364). Therefore, dissent and critique of governance is the essence of democracy. Multiple governance models in India for the Centre, states, union territories, Panchayats and special provisions for some units on various grounds keep the State intact. Providing autonomy to the various units under the country provides them with enough space to fulfil their local ambitions by maintaining harmony with the Centre.

For Barbora, autonomy is an expression for the "search of a political alternative. The language of autonomy is articulated as an integral element of the politics around issues of gender, ethnicity, class, race, and caste in India" (Barbora). Ranbir Samaddar elaborates on the convergence and divergence between democracy and autonomy:

The lesson is that autonomy cannot be considered as an exceptional measure to be taken in doses to make democracy acceptable; it must be the historical-political ingredient with which democracy is to be built. Thus notions of federalism, devolution of power, minority protection, rights of the indigenous people, and legal pluralism must now be combined and put in a collective form known as the politics of autonomies. Like all other aspects of democracy the principle and the politics of autonomy is also contentious, and like all other principles and arrangements, this too is subject to governmental manipulation, negotiation, and contest (Samaddar).

The Economist Intelligence Unit publishes Democracy Index since 2006, which analyses the five categories: "electoral process and pluralism; the functioning of government; political participation; political culture; and civil liberties" covering almost 165 countries. India dropped to 51st position in 2019 Democracy Index decelerating

by ten ranks and has been categorised under the “flawed democracy”. “An erosion of civil liberties in the country” has been considered as the primary reason for the democratic regression of India (The Economist Intelligence Unit 16). It shows that India has not yet achieved the status of “full democracy” where 22 countries like Norway, Iceland and Sweden finds the place.

Crucial Role of Civil Society

Active and informed civil society is of utmost importance for maintaining the vibrant democracy. David Held argues that a “democracy would be fully worth its name if citizens had the actual power to be active as citizens” means rights should be considered “integral to the very notion of democratic rule itself”. It presupposes the idea that “certain socio-economic conditions for the possibility of effective democratic participation” would be ensured to “operationalize a radical system of rights” (Held 183). According to Neera Chandhoke, civil society in the form of social associations brings “people together in multiple projects” to “engender and nurture solidarity and empathy”. Their projects “might simply intend to enhance sociability and dissipate alienation” (Chandhoke 41). The process of ‘double democratization’ indicates the “interdependent transformation of both state and civil society”. It should be based on the principle of division between the state and civil society and the notion that “the power to make decisions must be free of the inequalities and constraints imposed by the private appropriation of capital” (Held 182).

Under the ‘democratic autonomy’ model, David Held argues that proposed system of rights would involve “not only equal rights to cast a vote, but also equal rights to enjoy the conditions for enlightened understanding, involvement in all stages of collective decision-making and the setting of the political agenda” (Held 183). Many civil society movements in India have achieved success and raised the issues of utmost importance. Chipko movement successfully attempted to prevent the destruction of forests in the Himalayas, thereby shifting the discourse towards ‘ecology is the permanent economy’ stressing sustainable development-based model. Similarly, Narmada Bachao Andolan against the construction of a huge dam on Narmada river raised the more significant debate on ecology versus development in the country. Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender (LGBT) movement running for decades in India finally got success when Supreme Court gave the verdict on the decriminalisation of homosexuality in September 2018 that “Section 377 was unconstitutional in so far as it criminalises consensual sexual conduct between adults of the same sex” (Sanghvi). These few examples of civil society movements show the inherent strength of the common people in changing the existing discourse.

Despite some of the success in achieving a more democratic and inclusive society, still, there is a long way to go. Indian civil society needs to raise more significant questions to the policymakers regarding the true essence of governmentality, which takes care of welfare policies and existential issues as well. In this regard, Chandhoke questions the passivity of Indian civil society by elaborating that:

Authoritarian governments have delivered social and economic goods to their people and done so better, consider Singapore. What they have not delivered is the equal right of participation to the people. Concentration just on the delivery of social goods can miss out on vital aspects of democracy – the mobilisation of citizens into awareness of their political competence; that they have the right to participate in a public discourse on how things are and how they should be (Chandhoke 44).

There is another dimension also to the assertion of the civil society movements. Although active civil society is essential, if a certain part of the civil society achieves disproportionate amount of power, it may create obstructions in the functioning of a healthy democracy. According to David Held, there is a need to curtail the power of corporations and powerful interest groups which may constrain and influence the political agenda. It is imperative as “powerful sets of social relations and organizations” can “by virtue of the very basis of their operations distort democratic processes and hence outcomes” (Held 184). It may include some industry or some trade union or some influential social group, which can erode the democratic autonomy of the country. Therefore, a delicate balance needs to be maintained so that Indian democracy can thrive, accommodating the diverse issues of the country.

Patriarchal Politics and Women’s Quest for Autonomy

As per the Article 243 D of the Indian Constitution, “1/3rd of the Seats of Panchayati Raj Institutions and 1/3rd offices of the Chairpersons at all level of Panchayati Raj Institutions covered by Part IX of the Constitution are reserved for women” (Government of India). It has resulted in raising the autonomy of women in the decision-making arena, which is essential for the full participation of the women in the economy of the country. The study proves that “the reservation of a council seat affects the types of public goods provided” as “leaders invest more in infrastructure that is directly relevant to the needs of their own genders” (Chattopadhyay and Duflo 1409). It has been observed that the elected women leaders of Panchayats “invest more in the public goods more closely linked to women’s concerns: drinking water and roads in West Bengal and drinking water in Rajasthan” (Chattopadhyay and Duflo 1440).

Despite the considerable success of women reservation at local Panchayats, no consensus has been reached till date over the reservation for women in *Lok Sabha* where real power for law-making resides. Women are “handicapped by patriarchy and lack of private property” and search their “freedom in economic independence in work” (Patnaik). Women in India are facing various forms of violence ranging from domestic, public, physical, emotional to mental. Considering the realities of India, one cannot deny the fact that “women have fear of violence in their mind which causes the lack of participation in various areas of life” (Bhartiya Stree Shakti 14). Siwach argues that even “the police system, like any other institution in India, has been engulfed in gender biases, with social trends of victim blaming and societal shaming”. Therefore, “women hesitate from reporting crimes of sexual abuse to a large extent, based on the belief that the police is not going to take any

action” (Siwach). It has been noted that “social backwardness and religious conservativeness have reduced the strength of decision making power of women compared to men in India” (Banerjee and Roy 1040). The all-pervasive challenging situations for women show the real patriarchal face of Indian politics, where the concern for women safety has not been prioritised.

Broader Conception of Justice

The conception of justice is an essential component of any rational society. The vital importance of justice can be emphasised through the argument of John Rawls that “justice is the first virtue of the social institutions, as truth is of systems of thought”. In addition to it, a new alternative idea of ‘autonomy of autonomies’ provides the much-needed strength in ensuring justice by providing autonomy to the units at several levels. It has been suggested that:

As an alternative to a monolithic ‘Autonomy’ associated with a particular demand for power-sharing, can we visualize ‘Autonomy of autonomies’ as an ongoing democratisation process from below, involving multi-spatial, multi-temporal, and multi-system interaction among institutions which blend the different forms of organizational reach; a process dictated and driven by a facilitative-enabling conception of power (as a medium) rather than a state-centric, instrumental conception of power (over others) which is delegated or distributed from a centralized point to authoritative locations across a given territory (Chaturvedi).

For David Held, the central concern of ‘rule of law’ should be about “distributional questions and matters of social justice” for the actual realisation of democratic rule. It means that besides the formal equality of law, the actual capacity like health and resources needs to be ensured so that citizens may take full advantage of the opportunities (Held 184). However, India has not been able to harness its demographic dividend fully. Legal justice attempts to pave the way for social justice. There have been many shortcomings in the judicial system of India, which requires considerable attention. The words of William Goldstone that ‘justice delayed is justice denied’ finds actual relevance in the Indian context where the judiciary is overburdened with cases and delayed settlement of cases. As per the 2018 National Crime Records Bureau Report, total 3,23,537 undertrial prisoners (people who were waiting for trial or whose trials were still ongoing, and who have not been convicted) are lodged in Indian prisons (National Crime Records Bureau, MHA 35). Moreover, as per the 2017 Amnesty International report, India’s “undertrial population has a disproportionate number of Muslims, Dalits and Adivasis. About 53% of undertrials are from these communities, which make up 39% share of the population of India” (Amnesty International India 5). Dalits “suffering from cast bondages are also by and large property-less in India” (Patnaik). They do not possess adequate knowledge and financial capability to file cases in the court and get legal help, which mostly results in the worse scenario, where many of them have to languish in jails. Even

78th Law Commission Report has noted that “the jails should primarily be meant for lodging convicts and not for persons under trial” (Law Commission of India 6).

In January 2018, the four senior judges of the Supreme Court questioned the leadership of the then Chief Justice of India Dipak Misra in a press conference, criticising him for misuse of power. Such a press conference happened for the first time in India. One of the four judges, Justice Chelameshwar said that “the nation’s top court was not in order and they were left with no choice but to address the nation after they failed to convince the Chief Justice” (The Economic Times). Such incidents show the broader malaise in the judicial system, which needs to be tackled at the earliest.

Role of Institutions

The institutions play a very crucial role in the positive development of a country. Institutions can be considered as vital stakeholders in the welfare of the citizens of the country. Governments come and go at regular and irregular intervals, but institutions are supposed to remain intact. To accommodate the vast differences of Indian democracy, institutions have played a key role by discouraging centrifugal tendencies.

Kanchan Chandra argues that inclusion of people can be achieved even in an ethnically divided democracy by designing “institutions of interpretation such as the census which allow individuals who find themselves in an ethnic minority the option of reinventing themselves as members of at least one majority ethnic category”. She further suggests that “designing institutions of competition such as party and electoral systems which encourage ethnic self-reinvention in the political sphere” is the second step for the purpose of inclusion (Chandra). Such steps attempt to incorporate the citizens to make them inalienable part of the country.

In the Indian context, it has been observed that “the misuse of President’s Rule, a constitutional provision that allows the center to suspend elected institutions and to place states under central rule, constitutes a vertical threat”. Moreover, “horizontal threats emerge when actors outside the political system subvert elected institutions. In India, non-state armed groups have often called for a boycott of election, and have at times succeeded in disrupting the electoral process systematically and violently” (Harbers, Bartman and Wingerden 1155). These are the centrifugal tendencies which alienate and marginalise certain sections of the community, which poses a long-term danger to the unity and stability of the country.

Institutional autonomy is the key to achieve the welfare of the citizens and the proper functioning of democracy. However, there are many instances where India has found decay in the autonomy of Institutions. For instance, the Election Commission of India was not fulfilling its mandated role until T.N. Seshan took over the command of the Commission. He was the chief election commissioner from 1990 to 1996 and transformed the functioning of the election commission. Seshan is credited with “effectively implementing the model code of

conduct for the first time, reining in muscle and money power in elections, filing cases and arresting candidates for not abiding by polling rules, and suspending officials for aligning with candidates” (Dhingra). Because of his efforts, the autonomy and sanctity of the whole institution are appreciated all over the world.

There is ample evidence in the public domain to show the government interferences in the functioning of many autonomous institutions. For instance, in 2013, the Supreme Court of India termed the Central Bureau of Investigation (CBI) “a caged parrot” for lack of functional autonomy from the outside interference (Venkatesan). Considering such cases, it is imperative to contemplate that any attempt to erode the institutional autonomy causes irreparable damage to the “larger national interest when professional merit and integrity are compromised and institutional memory is distorted, devalued and often discarded” (Jayakumar).

Conclusion

After studying various scenarios of Indian democracy, it has been observed that patriarchal politics has adversely affected the prospects of empowerment of women in society. There is a need for the policies which can provide autonomy to the women. It will serve as a powerful centripetal force for the unity of the country where almost half of the population will participate in the economy of the country without any structural obstructions. As far as the autonomy of institutions is concerned, a mixed scenario has been observed. On some occasions, a decay has been observed in the autonomy of institutions while significant improvement has been seen on various occasions. Institutional autonomy is the key to the preservation of certain ideals which strive for the sanctity of the State and binds citizens under the social contract. Although civil society in India has many successes to its credit, its full potential has not yet been harnessed due to the lack of awareness about its strength. The legitimacy of the State increases when it adopts plural frameworks of autonomy for the proper functioning of the democratic institutions in the country.

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